

**HCV Study Initiation Package, including study protocol
Deliverable D3.1**

11.2023 (Revised March 2025)

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***Legend** = Role in the Project: **C** – Coordinator // **B** – Beneficiary // **AP** – Associated Partner // Organization Type: **RTD** – Research and Technological Development// **PHI** – Public Health Institution // **Hosp** – Hospital // **SME** – Small and medium-sized enterprises. // **LC** – Large Company // **NGO** – Non-Governmental Org.

	Work Packages Name	WP Leader
1	WP1 Coordination and Management	UNIBO
2	WP2 Gastric Cancer Prevention Through Helicobacter Pylori Screening and Treatment	FINBA
3	WP3 Liver Cancer Prevention Through HCV Screening and Treatment	INSP
4	WP4 Prevention of Cancers Associated with HPV Infection	RAPH BB
5	WP5 Behavioural and Sociocultural Assessment	SDU
6	WP6 Cost Effectiveness Analysis	RPA Prague
7	WP7 Dissemination, Outreach and Exploitation	WEDO

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5	Regional Authority of Public Health Banská Bystrica	RAPH BB	
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How to quote this document

Pilot study protocol for the Hepatitis C screening and treatment in occupational health settings (CPW D3.1)

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is Deliverable 3.1 (“HCV Study Initiation Package, including study protocol”) of the CANCER PREVENTION AT WORK project. It is issued under the responsibility of The National Institute of Public Health, Bucharest, Romania (INSP) with the contribution of a working group comprising principal investigators and team members from the implementation centers in Italy, Romania, Slovakia and principal investigators from partners in Denmark, Germany, Czech Republic and Spain.

The CPW intervention for liver cancer prevention by targeting hepatitis C infection prevention, diagnosis and treatment will be conducted on four different occupational cohorts of minimum 1000 participants (health care workers, retail and finance workers, and metal workers) in the context of routine medical surveillance carried out in occupational health settings

Prevention of hepatitis C at work is normally available only for occupational groups at risk for biological hazards, following specific rules and procedures adopted by each country under the health and safety laws and regulations. However, the routine medical examinations are carried out for many other occupational groups, within the occupational health settings. This can be an opportunity to offer rapid hepatitis C testing to all workers, no matter their risks, complemented by adequate counselling on lifestyle and behavioral changing that can help prevent infectious-related liver cancer. Moreover, in case of positive test results, the recommendation for link with precise diagnosis and treatment will be available immediately together with recommendation for testing of the household members.

The success of such a micro-elimination intervention in occupational health services was little explored. Therefore, the D3.1 consists in a protocol of a multicenter, multinational interventional pilot study aimed at building several types of working cohorts in which to assess the feasibility of hepatitis C prevention through test and cure. The results will be monitored in a follow-up stage.

The protocol, which has been discussed and agreed with all the WP3 partners, will be submitted for local ethical evaluation. Each partner in its own country will undergo necessary procedures for obtaining the approval by local Ethics Committee.

The intended audience of this deliverable consists of members of the CPW consortium and the European Commission.

2 SYNOPSIS

WP3 Protocol working group	D. Mates, F. Popescu, L. Calugareanu, S. Teodorescu, A. Neamtu, I. Crull, M. G. Bunescu, B. A. Vinersar, M. Oțelea, A. Rașcu, R. Bogdan Mateescu, C. Grigoropol, C. Mandanach, M. Audičová, P. Boffetta, A. Cataneo, F. Piscaglia, I. Serio, M. Seyyedsalehi, M. Sassano, A. Cosmin, M. V. Picciaiola, E. Fabiánová, J. Strhársky, L. Maďarová, A. Schneider-Kamp, T. Rageliene, A. Honrado, R. Vilček, J. Garajová, M. Jendrušáková, E. Púchyová, V. Pohančaniková, L. Mojžišová, Zuzana Bečková, Viktória Ďurajová, Egle Gorra, M. Venturini, E. Stocco, A. Godono, V. De Pasquale, E. Carena, G. Sanguinetti, M. Wensing, C. Roth, D. Vencovsky, E. Berti, M. Bernardini, E. Murínová, E. Kapustíková, M. Kočtúchová Blažinová, L. Latináková, L. Kamenská, B. Korbelová, R. Gili, R. Cristaudo, P. Pavanelli, R. Brambila, M. Elisabetta Scarvaglieri, C. Porpiglia, I. Hasanaj
Project Coordinator	Paolo Boffetta, UNIBO
Study rationale	Pilot intervention, targeted to test the feasibility of the prevention of Hepatitis C infection-related cancers, which will be conducted within the framework of existing occupational health surveillance program in five centres, on four different workers groups. The intervention will follow the World health Organisation (WHO) guidelines consisting in: hepatitis C virus (HCV) serological testing, confirmation of current infection and treatment of positive subjects. After 6 months, a follow-up will be conducted to record the compliance with treatment and results.
Study design	Multicentre, prospective, interventional pilot study (testing for HCV and follow-up of positive for adherence to precise diagnosis and treatment)
Study population	Health care workers (HCW), metal workers, retail workers, finance institution workers undergoing routine occupational health surveillance at workplace
Inclusion criteria	Age>18 years, providing informed consent to participate
Exclusion criteria	Unable to consent, current treatment for HCV, any conditions that prevent serological testing for HCV antibodies
Timeline	24 months enrolment, 12 months follow-up
Partners involved	UNIBO, INSP, SRMM, Col Hosp, RAPH BB, SDU, FDRH, ISP, UNITO, UKHD, ZP, FLAT, RER, ASL TO

3 LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
CPW	Cancer Prevention at Work project
DAA	Direct Antiviral Agents
DMP	Data management plan
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
GP	General practitioner
HCC	Hepatic Cellular Carcinoma
HCV	Hepatitis C virus
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
Hp	Helicobacter pylori
HPV	Human Papilloma Virus
ID	Identification number
IFU	Instructions for use
NAT	Nucleic Acid Test
OH	Occupational health
PI	Principal investigator
RNA	Ribonucleic acid
WP	Work Package

4 LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: The testing algorithm for hepatitis C

Figure 2: Overall flow-chart of the study

5 LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Description of the implementation centres for HCV

Table 2: Prevention and health promotion initiatives in the implementation centres

Table 3: Resources dedicated to the project in the implementation centres

Table 4: Laboratory facilities

Table 5: Link with precise diagnosis and cure

6 INTRODUCTION

6.1 Project introduction

Chronic infections represent a major cause of human cancer: on a global scale, they are responsible for an estimated 13% of human cancers. *Helicobacter pylori* (Hp), Hepatitis C virus (HCV), and Human Papilloma Virus (HPV) are responsible together for 75% of these cases, or 10% of total cancer burden¹. Occupational health (OH) surveillance is mandatory in all European countries: although the mechanisms of its implementation vary between the countries, these programs are in general aimed at diagnosing and preventing work-related diseases. Prevention of occupational cancers has therefore been a component of OH surveillance. In recent years, however, there has been a movement towards including in OH surveillance aspects of health promotion which are not occupational in a strict sense. This approach stems from several considerations: (i) the contact between the worker and the health professional in charge of the surveillance can be seen as a privileged opportunity for health promotion in general; (ii) through the worker, the health promotion initiative may reach other groups of the population; (iii) because of the periodic nature of the visits entailed by the OH surveillance, it is possible to efficiently implement follow-up mechanisms. In WP3, the conceptual framework of the proposed research is based on the incorporation into on-going OH surveillance schemes of primary prevention programs against infection with HCV. The overarching objectives of the proposed research are: to conduct a pilot project aimed at assessing the feasibility and effectiveness (including cost-effectiveness) of incorporating primary prevention intervention against HCV into existing occupational surveillance systems including its impact beyond the workers directly involved in the pilot project; to identify opportunities, barriers and bottlenecks for the implementation of such interventions. This action is part of the Cancer Mission cluster of projects on “Prevention and early detection”.

6.2 Objectives of WP3 and tasks

The overarching objective of WP3 is the implementation of HCV screening and treatment of infection, as primary prevention of HCC, within OH surveillance programs.

The Specific Objectives of WP3 include:

O3.1 To design a protocol for screening and treatment for HCV infection of workers involved in occupational health surveillance, including follow-up and screening of family members of HCV-positive workers;

O3.2 To coordinate the implementation of the pilot project on HCV infection prevention in several centres participating in CPW;

O3.3 To analyse the data collected within the pilot projects; Based on the results of the pilot projects, to develop plans for large-scale implementation of HCV infection prevention within occupational health surveillance systems.

O3.4 To engage the national and regional stakeholders in the implementation and adaptation of country tailored preventive interventions for HCC related to HCV infection in the current practice of occupational medicine.

The objectives of WP3 will be reached by completing the following tasks:

Task 3.1. Identification and evaluation of current national/regional programs for prevention of HCV infection and HCC;

Task 3.2. Design of a protocol for a pilot study on screening and treatment for HCV infection of workers involved in occupational health surveillance, including screening of household members of HCV-positive workers;

Task 3.3. Implementation and coordination of the pilot project on HCV screening and treatment in selected centres participating in CPW

Task 3.4. Analysis of data collected within the pilot projects on HCV screening on determinants of HCV infection and effectiveness of intervention

¹ De Martel C., Georges D., Bray F., Ferlay J., Clifford GM. Global burden of cancer attributable to infections in 2018: a worldwide incidence analysis. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2020;8: e180-e190.

Task 3.5. Development of plans for large-scale implementation of HCV infection prevention within OH surveillance systems

Task 3.6. Identification of the best strategies to increase the adherence of European working populations to the program of screening and treatment of HCV infection.

6.3 Contents of the deliverable D 3.1

Deliverable 3.1 is a public report and contains the protocol developed by the WP3 working group for the prevention of liver cancer by pilot intervention to prevent hepatitis C through screening and treatment. The protocol is designed in accordance with the specifications of task 3.2.

7 BACKGROUND

7.1 Study rationale and outcomes

The primary goal of the pilot study is to investigate the feasibility, performance and cost-effectiveness of prevention interventions targeted toward HCV related liver cancer, within the framework of occupational health surveillance programs.

The outcomes of the pilot study are:

- prevalence and determinants of HCV infection in different occupational groups (health care workers, retail and service workers, finance workers, metal workers)
- behavioural and sociocultural assessment of the barriers and facilitators of the intervention
- acceptability of the intervention by the recipients: participation rate, acceptance rate
- follow up of positives to assess the adherence to diagnosis procedures and treatment, completion of treatment and cure
- acceptability of the intervention by the deliverers (occupational health providers)

7.2 Expected impact

Available literature suggests that screening and eradication of HCV have the potential to be cost-effective, albeit not in all cases. Cost-effectiveness ratios in the literature vary and depend on a number of factors, such as the targeting of the intervention (high risk vs low risk group). There is thus a need to improve our understanding of the impact that the design of such interventions (especially in the European context) and structural conditions can have on cost-effectiveness. In addition, there is a significant need to improve the evidence base for public health interventions implemented within the framework of OH surveillance, with the vast majority of cost-effectiveness evidence not being specific for such interventions. This is particularly significant given the potential for OH surveillance to be a comparatively more cost-effective tool for the relevant interventions. If the results of the pilot studies will be successful and cost-effective, the research group, together with relevant stakeholders, will be able to provide guidance and recommendations for large-scale implementation of the intervention.

Another expected impact to be considered in the development, evaluation of feasibility and implementation of this new health intervention is the assessment of acceptability as a multi-faceted construct that involves both the intervention recipients and the providers.

At baseline we will assess the acceptability of the intervention within the study subjects and in the follow up we will collect information about adherence to diagnosis and treatment, using standardised questionnaires. Apart from assessing acceptability, we will be able to evaluate other aspects such as dropout rates, all-cause discontinuation, reason for discontinuation and withdrawal rates.

Similar, for health care providers (doctors, nurses) we will use pre- and post-intervention harmonized questionnaires to document problems and chances for a successful implementation from their perspective.

7.3 Study design

The intervention will be implemented as a prospective pilot study for HCV micro-elimination in various occupational groups and workplace settings, and will target a minimum of 1000 workers in each

participating country and centre. The intervention will follow the WHO's 2022 updated recommendations for simplified service delivery and HCV diagnostics².

During the routine medical examination at work, workers will be invited to participate in the pilot study by taking an HCV rapid test and by responding to baseline questionnaires. A single HCV antibodies assay that meets the minimum safety, quality and performance standards, specified in the WHO list of prequalified in vitro diagnostic products³, will be used by the occupational physician for each worker. Following a reactive HCV antibody serological test result, the physician will recommend next steps that will link the suspected diseased worker to supplementary interventions for diagnosis of viraemic infection and cure. The occupational physician will recommend the test also to the household members of positive workers.

Workers diagnosed with hepatitis C will be contacted within 6-12 months directly or by email or telephone and will be asked to complete a follow-up questionnaire regarding their general health status, the diagnostic and therapeutic actions undertaken for cure.

7.4 Study implementation centres description

The study is implemented as a pilot intervention in different countries and occupational settings and will target various occupational group with various risk levels. A brief description of the implementation centres is presented in Table 1.

In many companies, the employers organize local prevention and health promotion programs for the workers, independent on the biological risk profile of the workplaces. Such past or current initiatives may change the worker's perception and behaviour toward a healthier lifestyle. Table 2 describes such existing programs in the implementation centres.

Also, the context of occupational health surveillance (organisation, staff, laboratory facilities) is different between and within countries. Tables 3 and 4 summarize these aspects.

Moreover, the medical services provided for subjects who are suspected for an acute or chronic viral hepatitis are different. The link between positive screening and precise diagnosis and treatment follows different pathways, via the GP or specialised services from the hospitals. In the Italian centres this role is covered by local health authorities (Table 5).

Given these multi-faceted aspects of the implementation centres, it is important that the study protocol takes into account the local specific and allows a certain amount of flexibility in its implementation. Also, the planned and realized set-up of the procedures need to be well-documented by each implementation centre for a good interpretation of the research findings.

7.5 Communication and training activities

In order to enhance the evidence-based knowledge of key groups (companies' managers, workers) on the prevention of hepatitis C related cancer and the confidence in the curative actions for hepatitis C, various educational, informative materials (e.g., booklets, leaflets, posters), tailored to specific audience, will be prepared at project level, will be translated in the local languages and disseminated in the implementation centres, prior to the start of the recruitment. These planned and realized informational and educational implementation activities need to be well documented by each implementation centre for a good interpretation of the research findings.

All OH teams will be trained locally on the standard procedures of the HCV intervention protocol.

Another key component of the HCV intervention will aim additional training of the OH teams with a focus on personal communication skills, HCV prevention guidance and counselling services. These activities will be organized at project level and locally. The emphasis will be on how to enhance the worker's motivation to participate in the study and how to offer counselling to positive workers and their family's member.

² Updated recommendations on HCV simplified service delivery and HCV diagnostics: policy brief. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2022. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO.

³ <https://extranet.who.int/prequal/vitro-diagnostics/prequalified-vitro-diagnostics>

7.6 Data sharing

Data generated at different stages of the pilot study will be managed, organized and released using procedures and infrastructure that are being developed in the DMP, describing the principles, standards, methods process and policies regarding the storage, curation, and dissemination of the data collected in CPW under FAIR principles. The data management at local level is under the responsibility of the specific partner who generated the data.

The data sharing procedures, including measures to guarantee privacy and data protection, are subject to a joint data controller agreement between all the research teams involved in the project.

7.7 Ethics

HCV testing is based on well-established approaches (screening for the anti-HCV antibody followed by confirmation of active infection by HCV RNA) that accurately detects HCV infection. There is adequate evidence that first time testing in all adults and periodic testing for those at risk for reinfection are beneficial.

There are potential harms described in relation to screening itself: anxiety, fear of been labelled or discriminated. However, the overall harms of a positive test are considered to be lower than the benefits.

In our protocol, we considered two key facilitators to minimise the potential harms: raising awareness and education of both deliverers (research staff) and recipients (workers). Enhanced worker education will be ensured by actively disseminating informative materials (flyers, brochures, newsletter) at workplace, meetings of workers with project staff, before and during the intervention. The deliverers (occupational physicians and nurses) will be trained to gain communication skills and to play the role of a healthcare navigator, guiding positive employees inside the local healthcare system. These activities will minimise the harms and increase the potential benefits by timely linking the initial positive test with complete, precise diagnosis of viraemic infection and treatment. The research team will ensure the confidentiality of all information and no test results will be disclosed without the participant permission. The intervention must be carried out in line with the ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles. Patient's informed consent template, comprising the minimum items required by the intervention, has been developed. Implementation centres can adapt it or use local variant, provided that all national legal and ethical requirements are met. Questionnaires and forms to collect data from the participant have been developed by a working group comprising the PIs and other specialists from each implementation centre, and are annexed to this protocol. Each centre is responsible with the translation/adaptation of these documents to the local languages and context. A pilot test on a subset subject of the intended population to validate the questionnaires will take place in each centre/country.

The intervention requires appropriate local ethical approval. Once ethical and administrative authorizations are in place, the intervention can start in the implementation centre.

8 STUDY POPULATION AND ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Where: Participating OH services

Who: OH staff and the local research team

What: Consent form, clinical, demographical, lifestyle and outcome data

How: Interview with the patient using standard questionnaire, self-administrated questionnaire, data abstracted from OH medical records, etc.

The purpose of this chapter is to outline standardized procedures for subjects' recruitment and collection of biological samples and clinical data, to eliminate major discrepancies between centres. All information is collected from workers invited to participate in the project and that have given their specific consent to participate in the HCV intervention, or their general consent to participate to parallel interventions in CPW, when the consent provided is consistent with them. Ongoing or retrospective

HCV interventions in the participating centres can contribute to CPW if their followed protocol(s) is (are) consistent with these guidelines.

Prospective recruitment of all subjects will take place according to the following strategy:

- The recruitment process is set to begin in M13 of the project (May 2024) and is expected to continue for a duration of 12 to 24 months, during which all eligible subjects will be invited to participate in the screening procedures;
- The subject is identified before or during the OH regular visit and its eligibility to the study is confirmed;
- The subject is informed of the study (scope, objective, procedures, results, etc.) and if she/he agree to participate, she/he is requested to complete and sign the informed consent form;
- A baseline questionnaire is administered by a trained interviewer from the occupational health staff. A self-administrated questionnaire is given to each participant to be completed in a pseudo-anonymized form. These questionnaires are completed on the implementation site, ensuring privacy of respondent and are collected in special closed box/envelope. The study staff explain the content and assist the respondent if questions or queries arise;
- An assay test for hepatitis C antibodies is performed according to the producer specification. Details on the samples are recorded in a special format;

For those testing positive, the immediate link to precise diagnosis and treatment is recommended by the OH doctor, following the local practice and procedure, and clinical protocols for hepatitis C diagnosis and treatment, available in each centre/country (Table 5).

The subjects with a positive diagnosis of hepatitis C are followed after six to twelve months to collect data on the treatment and post treatment evaluation (using questionnaires) (Table 5).

The family members of those diagnosed with hepatitis C, living in the same household, will be contacted and invited to receive counselling and recommendation for screening, via general practitioner, specialized medical service, other services, according to the current local practice.

Eligibility criteria for index subjects:

- Age > 18 years
- Workers under OH surveillance
- Consent to participate

Exclusion criteria:

- subjects are excluded if there is no means of obtaining an adequate venous blood sample as per the protocol requirements
- subjects are excluded if they have any condition that could interfere with their ability to provide informed consent such as dementia or severe cognitive impairment
- subjects who are diagnosed with hepatitis C and are under specific treatment

Timeline

We envisage the official start of the recruitment will be May 2024. According to the project timeline, recruitment is anticipated to conclude by M36. The Grant Agreement specifies that the completion of recruitment for pilot studies is scheduled for M36, with follow-up activities extending beyond this period and estimated up to months 37–42 of the project. In some recruitment centres, particularly those delivering more than one intervention (in addition to HCV), the enrolment period may be extended until the full planned timeframe is completed.

Sample size justification:

A total of 1,000 workers will be included in each center. This sample size will be sufficient to provide evidence of effectiveness of the intervention with a standard error of 0.08%, assuming 2% workers with infection, 80% participation rate, 70% adherence to the treatment, and 80% efficacy of the treatment. The p-value of the comparison with a control population with 0.05 spontaneous clearance or treatment (controls) is < 0.001. These estimates will be compared with actual proportions of participation, adherence, efficacy and prevalence of infection measured during the progress of the project

9 ENROLLMENT AND DATA COLLECTION

9.1 Approach of index subjects and collection of baseline data

Workers aged 18 or more should be approached before or during the routine OH medical visit, preferably when the visit is scheduled. Informative materials explaining the purpose of the study will be distributed at workplace to facilitate the understanding of the study objectives and acceptance of the study procedures. During the OH medical visit, the OH doctor will discuss with each worker and will give more details on HCV prevention through screening and treatment. The timeline of the OH medical visits will depend on the local practice in each implementation site.

Eligible subjects accepting to participate in the study will be asked to read and sign a consent form (Annex 1), which describes the study background and explain the procedures. Each participating centre will be responsible for archiving participants' consent forms.

Next, information on specific risk factors for hepatitis C, following the structure of the baseline questionnaire provided in Annex 2, will be taken during clinical consultation by an interviewer (doctor, nurse, researcher) or will be abstracted from the OH medical records. General rules for the interview are included in the questionnaire and special training of the interviewers will take place locally. The baseline questionnaire can be completed online.

Personal sensitive information on behavioural risk factors will be collected using a self-administrated pseudo-anonymous questionnaire (Annex 3). These questionnaires are distributed to each participant, are completed on site, ensuring adequate privacy, and are collected by the research team in special closed box/envelope.

A special section of this questionnaire will be dedicated to collect participants' subconscious subjective perception of his/her health capital resources, using the projective technique. The interviewer will present to participants the task and give instructions on how to do it. The details of the protocol for the projective technique to assess worker's self-perceived health capital are presented in Annex 4.

All the questionnaires will be translated/adapted to the local language and tested/validated locally.

During the same OH visit, the biological samples will be collected, processed and tested for HCV antibodies, following the study centre own standard operation procedure in place. The laboratory assay report with the results of the test will be communicated to the study subject as soon as possible, by the medical doctor, who will explain the results and discuss further options for those testing positive.

9.2 Testing algorithm

The testing sequence for identifying current hepatitis C will follow the current WHO's recommendation and will start with serological testing (rapid diagnostic test or laboratory-based immunoassay) offered to all eligible workers. A positive HCV antibody test indicates one of the following three scenarios: (1) active infection, (2) past HCV infection that has resolved, or (3) a false-positive test⁴. None of these anti-HCV antibody tests can differentiate whether the infection is new (acute), chronic, or no longer present. Therefore, confirmatory test of active infection is needed⁵. Molecular diagnostic tests for hepatitis C specifically detect HCV RNA and the process is commonly referred to as a Nucleic Acid Test (NAT) or Nucleic Acid Amplification Test (NAAT)⁶. The HCV NAT becomes positive approximately 1 to 2 weeks

⁴ Cloherty G, Talal A, Collier K, et al. Role of Serologic and Molecular Diagnostic Assays in Identification and Management of Hepatitis C Virus Infection. *J Clin Microbiol.* 2016; 54:265-73.

⁵ Oru E, Trickey A, Shirali R, Kanters S, Easterbrook P. Decentralisation, integration, and task-shifting in hepatitis C virus infection testing and treatment: a global systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet Global Health.* 2021;9: e431-e45.

⁶ Scott JD, Gretsch DR. Molecular diagnostics of hepatitis C virus infection: a systematic review. *JAMA.* 2007; 297:724-32.

after initial HCV infection⁷. The NAT test has become the gold standard supplemental test for patients who have a positive HCV EIA screening test. The testing algorithm is presented in Figure 1.

9.3 Link with precise diagnosis and treatment for subjects with a positive HCV antibodies test

All positive subjects will be counselled by the OH medical doctor regarding the hepatitis C causes, risk factors, available options for diagnosis and treatment.

All workers who tested positive and accepted the sharing of their results with other doctors, will be referred to the nearest available specialized medical unit for confirmation of hepatitis C infection using NAT or equivalent. Because the local medical practice and rules are different (Table 5), each study centre will develop a local procedure for this step and will keep track records on the referral of each participant to the diagnostic and treatment centre.

For those with a positive diagnosis of hepatitis C infection, the precise evaluation of disease stage, liver function and any other pre-treatment investigations will follow the clinical protocols in practice in each centre/country. Treatment option, follow-up and post-treatment evaluation will be established by the specialized medical doctors, according to the therapeutic protocols available in each centre/country. The implementation centres will seek to collect all available data on diagnosis, treatment and post-treatment evaluation, in a harmonized format.

The household members of workers diagnosed with hepatitis C will be contacted with the permission of the index subjects and will be invited to receive counselling and recommendation for screening via the medical services available locally.

9.4 Follow-up of subjects diagnosed with hepatitis C

The subjects diagnosed with hepatitis C will be invited for a follow-up visit at six to twelve months after the disease confirmation. The OH medical team will collect all available information on clinical and laboratory diagnosis, disease stage, recommended treatment and post treatment clinical evaluation using any available source (medical documents, reports, records, etc) (Table 5). The follow-up information will be recorded using a standardized form.

10 COLLECTION OF SPECIMENS, STORAGE, PREPARATION AND TESTING PROCEDURE

Where: in the OH service and/or local laboratory

Who: OH medical staff or laboratory trained technicians

What: one specimen (serum, plasma, whole venous/capillary blood) per subject

How: according to the product instructions for use

10.1 Purpose and scope of the procedure

The purpose of this chapter is to outline standardized procedures for WP3 intervention study to follow for biological specimen collection, processing and testing.

This procedure is intended to ensure that biological samples will be obtained from consented participants, in a safe and efficient manner, while eliminating the risks of contamination and loss.

The document does not describe how blood should be processed, stored and tested.

The document does not cover detailed safety procedures for handling blood and it is recommended that personnel follow institutional biosafety guidelines.

10.2 Material used, conditions of preservation and handling, test procedure

A serologic assay (rapid test or laboratory-based immunoassay) for the qualitative detection of specific antibodies to HCV present in human serum, plasma or whole blood, will be used in all implementation centres. The chosen commercial product/assay must be quality assured and accepted by the WHO on the list of prequalified in vitro diagnostic products.

⁷ Glynn SA, Wright DJ, Kleinman SH, et al. Dynamics of viremia in early hepatitis C virus infection. *Transfusion*. 2005; 45:994-1002.

For centres opting for a laboratory-based assay, the collection, preparation, storage and testing of the blood specimen will be done according to the IFU available for the product of choice. The blood specimens will be coded and labelled with the identification number of the subject. A special form aimed to facilitate the management of each biosample is presented in Annex 5.

11 RECORDING OF SCREENING/TEST RESULTS

Where: OH medical unit

Who: OH medical staff (medical doctor, research assistant)

What: reading the EIA HCV test results and interpretation of positive specimens

How: following the IFU provided by the product manufacturer and assessed by WHO

11.1 Purpose and scope of the procedure

The purpose of this chapter is to outline standardized procedures for HCV intervention to follow for recording and communicating to the subject the results of the screening test.

The document does not describe how the test results should be calculated, read and interpreted.

The tests should be handled only by qualified personnel trained in laboratory procedures, familiar with their potential hazards and strictly following the IFU.

11.2 Communication of the test results

The individual assay report of the HCV test will be handed out to each participant, according to the procedures available in each laboratory and OH medical unit. The OH medical staff have to take all necessary measures to ensure the confidentiality of test results. The OH doctor will directly discuss the results as soon as possible with each participant and will explain how the results should be interpreted. Test results will be recorded in the dedicated log sheet of each subject (Annex 5)

All positive subjects will be counselled by the OH doctor regarding the hepatitis C causes, risk factors, available options for diagnosis and treatment. The OH medical doctors and staff in each centre will receive local training on test interpretation and guidance on personal communication and counselling services offered to participants.

If the subject consent, the test results can be shared with the family members, other medical doctors with the purpose of speed up the next step of diagnosis for viraemic load and liver function.

12 COLLECTION OF CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT DATA (for subjects diagnosed with hepatitis C)

Where: OH medical unit

Who: OH medical staff (medical doctor, research assistant)

What: follow-up for diagnostic and treatment data

How: abstract from medical records, communication with the GPs, specialized treating doctors, interview (direct, telephone, email)

For positive patients consenting the use of their medical data, the research team will seek access to medical charts/records, disease reports, other sources, whichever is available according to the local practice, and will extract diagnosis and treatment information. The collaboration with the GPs/gastroenterologists/infectious disease specialists/other specialists who are in charge with the diagnosis and treatment of the patient, will be essential in this stage and will ensure the timely information on the disease evolution. Each centre will choose the preferred option such as direct communication or communication via medical letter, online, etc.

Data about the post treatment evaluation will reflect the HCV viral load at 12 weeks after completion of therapy. Other data can be collected optional (sustained viral response at 24 weeks, adverse effect of therapy, drug interactions, etc).

The data will be collected in a standardized form (Annex 6) based on what has been done at the time of data abstraction, not on what has been recommended.

Each subject diagnosed with hepatitis C, who consented to enter the follow-up, will be contacted after six months from enrolment and will be asked to fill in a small questionnaire aimed to capture the opinion and adherence to the diagnostic and treatment procedures. The questionnaire format is presented in Annex 7.

13 ARCHIVES AND COMPUTERIZED DATA

Where: OH medical unit

Who: OH medical staff (medical doctor, research assistant)

What: primary data collected via baseline and follow-up questionnaires, testing results, diagnostic and treatment data

How: archived in local centres according to local protocols and in line with the project's DMP

Each subject will be attributed with a unique identification number (ID).

The link with the name and other personal information will only be available to authorized staff of the local research team. Forms (hard copies) will be labelled with the corresponding ID and archived in local centres according to the protocols locally available and in line with the CPW project's DMP.

Each raw dataset collected in the implementation centres will be entered in the central data repository via RED Cap, using the eCRF developed by WP1. The management of data will follow the DMP.

14 OVERALL ENROLLMENT FLOWCHART

Effectively, all the stages of subject's recruitment (sample and data collection, screening, diagnosis) need an effective logging/tracking system in place so that at any time it is easy to see the status of the subjects and where they currently are in the overall process. This will allow monitoring of the process and receiving updates of what is happening. The Figure 2 describes the workflow for case selection.

15 OCCUPATIONAL HEALTHCARE AS A CONTEXT OF IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGIES AND OUTCOMES

15.1 Background

The CPW project is a study of the implementation of new healthcare practices. Implementation research is the scientific study of methods and strategies that facilitate or hinder the uptake of evidence-based practice and research into regular use. The field of implementation science aims at systematically closing the gap between what we know and what we do by identifying facilitator and addressing barriers related to the implementation of new healthcare practices. It also concerns the impact of implementation strategies (e.g. education of health professionals, reorganisation of working processes) on the uptake of recommended practices (e.g. offer people cancer screening, and follow-up actions if relevant) and contextual factors that influence the uptake (e.g. health professionals' competences, characteristics of the organization).

To evaluate the implementation aspects in this project, a process evaluation alongside the implementation will be carried out to capture the complexity inherent in cancer prevention at work. This process evaluation will provide the project with a greater, more in-depth understanding of why the intervention may be more or less effective. This process evaluation will assess the implementation strategies and contextual factors that influence implantation and sustainment (facilitator and barriers). These issues are usually measured with questionnaires for targeted health care professionals (occupational physicians and nurses in CPW). Ideally, the questionnaire is completed by all occupational healthcare providers who are involved in the implementation of preventive testing (physicians, nurses, managers etc.).

15.2 Proposed questionnaire for health providers at start and end of the CPW screening procedures

The questionnaires for occupational healthcare providers (Annexes 8 and 9), and the research team are developed by partner UKHD. The following factors will be assessed using a survey among occupational healthcare providers involved in the delivery of the intervention, patients who receive the intervention, and the local research teams:

Factors	Assessment method	When will data be collected:	Potential Participants:
Practices of screening and follow-up before start of project, incl. collaboration with primary care	Questionnaire for implementation centres	Before start	research teams in centres
Intervention Fidelity (=central implementation outcome)	Questionnaire developed for the specific screening procedure	Follow up	occupational healthcare providers
Context Factors that may have an impact on the implementation	Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR) Questionnaire (quantitative)	Baseline Follow-up	occupational healthcare providers
Barriers and facilitators for implementation	Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR) Questionnaire (quantitative)	Baseline Follow-up	occupational healthcare providers
Intervention Sustainability	Program Sustainability Assessment Tool	Follow-up	occupational healthcare providers
Documentation of planned and realized implementation strategies	Registration forms (e.g. participation in planned trainings, effective referrals for treatment)	Follow up	research teams in centres
Degree of uptake of recommended screening procedures	Questions on reach in the targeted populations	Follow up	research teams in centres

Depending on the local procedure, the questionnaires for healthcare workers and research teams can be subject to inclusion in the ethical application. For centralized data-analysis, data will be shared across centres (including the Heidelberg partner). This will be arranged in the data management plan of the project CPW.

16 ANNEXES

16.1 Annex 1 Informed consent template

INTRODUCTION

You are requested to participate in a study to investigate hepatitis C infection (HCV) at workplace. The study is being conducted by the Name of Local Implementation Centre and an international research consortium including universities and public health institutions from Italy, Spain, Romania, Slovakia, Denmark, Czech Republic, and Germany.

Your participation in this study is voluntary. You may refuse to participate or withdraw from the study at any time without this affecting in any way the medical surveillance at workplace that you are receiving.

Please read this consent form thoroughly and ask your occupational health doctor any questions you may have about the study before signing.

EXPLANATION OF PROCEDURES

If you agree to participate in this study, you will be asked to participate in an interview survey and provide a blood sample. In addition, we will ask your permission to collect relevant information from your medical records. No penalties will result if you decide not to respond, either to the information collection as a whole or to any particular question.

Questionnaire:

The occupational health doctor will come to administer the questionnaire during your routine medical check-up at the occupational health office. The interview takes approximately 30 minutes and consists of questions related to lifestyle, occupation and health. You will be asked also to read and answer a separate self-administrated questionnaire about your personal knowledge and habits.

Collection of blood:

You will be asked to donate a blood sample while you are in the occupational health office. A trained nurse will take a blood sample from your arm/finger in a routine manner.

What will your samples be used for:

Your blood samples will be completely de-identified. Your blood will be tested for the HCV antibodies. The laboratory will not have any information regarding your identity, and biological samples obtained will be used for research purposes only. Any material not immediately used will continue to be stored for use in future studies to help scientists learn more about hepatitis C infection. The research results are suitable for use as screening test for your medical care.

Could any of the results be relevant and useful for your health:

It is possible that during the analyses of your samples the research team may find results that suggest that you may have been in contact with the virus of hepatitis C at a certain point in your life.

However, the information produced by the blood testing is not reliable to make final/precise medical decisions about current disease/infection. For this reason, in the case of a positive result, the research team will provide you with a full package of information on the next steps to be followed for diagnosis confirmation and cure. It is possible that your general/family physician is interested in the HCV testing results produced and has the capacity to follow-up with additional testing and precise diagnosis procedure. If this is possible, you will be able to discuss this option with your doctor, while keeping at any time the right to decide not to disclose any results.

Sharing of data:

If you agree, results from HCV test, interview and medical data will be shared with other research teams for scientific purposes of the study.

COST AND COMPENSATION

There will be no cost to you for participating in this study, other than your time, and there is no compensation or payment for completing the questionnaire and providing biological samples.

POTENTIAL DISCOMFORT AND RISK

As for any blood collection, including those occurring during your routine clinical care, you may feel a little pain or develop a bruise on your arm at the puncture site. It is possible, but not likely, that there may be swelling or bleeding at the puncture site. There may be also uneasiness associated with needles. In the unlikely event of physical injury from drawing a blood sample, you will be provided with immediate medical treatment by the medical staff.

POTENTIAL BENEFITS

Hepatitis C is a serious disease if left undiagnosed and untreated. Hepatitis C can be completely cured if the diagnosis is made timely.

Although this is a research study, there will be direct benefits to you; by accepting the HCV testing you will be able to know your HCV infection status and in case of positive results you will be immediately guided by the medical staff for confirmation of diagnosis and treatment.

ASSURANCE OF CONFIDENTIALITY

The information concerning your participation in the study will be kept confidential and used only for scientific purposes, in accordance with applicable law of(Name of Country). No one, except members of the research team, will have access to your answers. No one, except members of the research team, will have access to your test results, in addition to your doctor if you so decide that s/he is provided with test results. Your employer will not be given any test results or information you provide us. Your biological samples will not be labelled with your name. Your name will not be used in any report or released in any way.

RIGHT TO WITHDRAW

Your participation in this medical research is voluntary and you may refuse to participate and/or withdraw your consent and discontinue participation at any time without penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled. If you initially decide to give permission to have biologic samples stored for future research purposes, but later change your mind by written notification to Name and address of local Principal Investigator, whatever remains of your biologic samples will then be destroyed. Your decision on this matter will not affect your medical care or employment.

CERTIFICATION

I have read the explanation about this study and have been given the opportunity to discuss it and to ask questions. By agreeing to participate in this study, I do not waive any rights that I may have regarding access to and disclosure of my records. I hereby consent to take part in the study components marked "yes" and refuse to consent to participate in the components marked "no". A copy of this consent form has been given to me.

YES	NO	Study Component
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Interview
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Blood sample collection, storage and HCV Testing
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Access to medical records and registry records
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sharing of data and HCV test results with other scientists for research purposes
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sharing of HCV test results data with your GP doctor
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sharing of HCV test results data with your first degree relatives

If we need to recontact you in the future to obtain extra information about diagnosis and cure, would you agree to this? Yes No

Signature of Participant

Date

Print Name

Print Name

We appreciate your cooperation in this important research project. If you have further questions about this study, you may call

Dr. (Name of Local Principal Investigator), at (Local Phone Number)

or you may write to him/her at the following address:

Name of Local Collaborating Centre and Address

16.2 Annex 2 Baseline questionnaire

BASELINE QUESTIONNAIRE

Introductory and explanatory text

Hepatitis is an inflammation of the liver that is caused by a variety of infectious viruses and non-infectious agents leading to a range of health problems, some of which can be fatal. There are five main strains of the hepatitis virus, referred to as types A, B, C, D and E.

In particular, types B and C lead to chronic disease in hundreds of millions of people and together are the most common cause of liver cirrhosis, liver cancer and viral hepatitis-related deaths.

The hepatitis C virus is a bloodborne virus and most infection occur through exposure to blood from unsafe injection practices, unsafe health care, unscreened blood transfusions, injection drug use and sexual practices that lead to exposure to blood (for example, people with multiple sexual partners and among men who have sex with men). HCV can be passed from an infected mother to her baby.

The virus can cause both acute and chronic hepatitis, ranging in severity from a mild illness to a serious, lifelong illness including liver cirrhosis and cancer.

Most people do not have symptoms in the first weeks after infection. It can take between two weeks and six months to have symptoms. When symptoms do appear, they may include: fever, feeling very tired, loss of appetite, nausea and vomiting, abdominal pain, dark urine, pale faeces, joint pain, jaundice (yellowing of the skin or eyes).

Because new HCV infections are usually asymptomatic, only few people are diagnosed when the infection is recent. In those people who develop chronic HCV infection, the infection is often undiagnosed because it remains asymptomatic until decades after infection when symptoms develop secondary to serious liver damage.

HCV infection is diagnosed in 2 steps:

1. Testing for anti-HCV antibodies with a serological test identifies people who have been infected with the virus.
2. If the test is positive for anti-HCV antibodies, a nucleic acid test for HCV ribonucleic acid (RNA) is needed to confirm chronic infection and the need for treatment.

There are effective treatments for hepatitis C. The goal of treatment is to cure the disease and prevent long-term liver damage. Antiviral medications, known as DAA, can cure more than 95% of cases if the disease is diagnosed timely. Some people's immune system can fight the infection on their own and new infections do not always need treatment. But treatment is always needed for chronic hepatitis C. People with hepatitis C may also benefit from lifestyle changes, such as avoiding alcohol and maintaining a healthy weight. With proper treatment, many people can be cured from hepatitis C infection and live healthy lives.

There is no effective vaccine against hepatitis C. The best way to prevent the disease is to avoid contact with the virus. Ways to prevent hepatitis C include:

- safe and appropriate use of healthcare injections
- safe handling and disposal of needles and medical waste
- testing of donated blood for the hepatitis C virus and other viruses
- training of health personnel
- practicing safe sex by using barrier methods such as condoms.
- harm-reduction services for people who inject drugs, such as needle exchange programs, substance use counselling and use of opiate agonist therapy (OAT)

Interview general rules

1. Before interview starts, please read the "Informed Consent" form and obtain the subject's signature, if possible, to the requested study components. Note that if the patient does not give consent to one component it will not be feasible to include the patient for that study component
2. Questions must be asked, as far as possible, as they are written. Answers must be written clearly
3. The columns should be filled in justified to the right
4. If you do not succeed in getting an answer or estimation, the columns should be filled in with 9 (or 99 where two-digit answers are possible)
5. Try not to influence the subject's reply to any extent, but read each question with calm and self-confidence. However, if you notice inconsistencies between responses, try to clarify
6. The local coordinator may add more values for some items. e.g., ethnic group, foreign language or a code for drinking volume of glasses, bottles. All local codes assigned must be provided with the final dataset
7. The accuracy of the questionnaire information is of absolute importance to the success of the study. The local coordinator should review all questionnaires for completeness and lack of inconsistencies. They also have the option to revisit any subject to confirm interview questions, should this be necessary

Subject Identification data

[The identification number should be used for the questionnaire and for any biological samples]

Subject ID |__|_|__|/|__|_|__|_|__|/|__|_|__|_|__|/|__|_|

Country ID_ (ex: Slovakia=SK, Romania=RO, Italy=IT)

Centre acronym_ RAPH; FDRH; ZPPO; UNIT; ASLT...

Intervention defined according to the intervention for which the subject is recruited (Hp, HCV, HPV) current number _____ four digits, starting from right to left i.e. 0001; 0002; 0003....

Example:

RO_COL HOSP_HCV_0001 = index subject from Romania, Colentina Hospital, recruited for HCV

SK_RAPH_HCV_HPV_0001= index subject from Slovakia, RAPH, recruited for HCV and HPV interventions

[For local use only – information won't be entered in CPW database]

Subject's contact address:

Telephone:

Email:

Full name of subject:

Interviewer name

Date of interview: |__|_|__|/|__|_|__|/|__|_|__|_|__|_| (DD/MM/YYYY)

Subject status: |__| (0=non-eligible, 1=index participant (worker); 2=participant (family member) 3=refusal)

If "3" please explain reason of refusal.....

Part 1: General information [N.B. some data can be abstracted from the OH medical records]

1.1 Sex (1=male, 2=female, 3=other/undisclosed) |__|

1.2 Date of birth

Day|__|_|__|Month |__|_|__|Year |__|_|__|_|__|_|

or

Age |__|_|__| [if date of birth not available, or not transferable]

1.3 Height (measured by the interviewer)

|__|_|__|_|__| cm

1.4 Weight (measured by the interviewer)

|__|_|__|_|__| kg

1.5 Nationality/Ethnicity (two digits codes) |__|_|__|

If other specify [Note to contributing study sites: list of ethnic groups to be defined locally]

1.6 Which foreign languages do you speak and at what level? |__|

1 = basic proficiency; 2 = good proficiency; 3 = mother tongue.

..... |__| Reading |__| Speaking |__| Writing

..... |__| Reading |__| Speaking |__| Writing

..... Reading Speaking Writing
 I don't speak any foreign language.

1.7 Highest education completed
0=none; 1=primary; 2=secondary (lower than university); 3=higher (university and higher);
9=Unknown/refuse to answer

1.8 Age at completion of full-time education | |

1.9 Residence | (1= rural; 2=urban)

1.10 What is your relationship status?

- single
- married
- cohabitating with a partner (but not married)
- divorced/separated
- widowed
- prefer not to disclose

1.11 Who do you cohabit with, i.e., who are you living with in one household? Please indicate the number of adult and children household members

- 1 adult
- 2-4 adults
- >4 adults
- number of children

Would you like to comment or add more details?.....

Part 2: Medical and reproductive history [N.B. data can be abstracted from the medical records]

2.1 Have you ever had any of the following diseases/conditions confirmed by a doctor?
(0=definitely or probably No; 1=definitely or probably Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes:

When it was first diagnosed (year, approximately)?

Were you prescribed a treatment by a doctor? (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

[To the interviewer – if treatment for HCV is ongoing, the subject is ineligible; ICD-0-3 code is added during data extraction]

	Disease	Year	Treatment If yes, which treatment (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)
2.1.1	Diabetes	_ _ _ _ _	_
2.1.2	Hepatitis B	_ _ _ _ _	_
2.1.3	Hepatitis C	_ _ _ _ _	_
2.1.4	Hepatitis D	_ _ _ _ _	_
2.1.5	HIV	_ _ _ _ _	_
2.1.6	Sexual transmitted infections (including HIV, HPV)	_ _ _ _ _	_
2.1.7	Renal failure	_ _ _ _ _	_
2.1.8	Hematological disorders	_ _ _ _ _	_
2.1.9	Organ, tissue, cell transplant	_ _ _ _ _	_
2.1.10	Cancer If yes: site of origin (topography according to ICD-O-3) [To the interviewer - ICD-O-3 code is added during data extraction] C _ _ _	_ _ _ _ _	_

2.2 Have you ever had blood transfusion? |_| (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)
If yes, when it was the last one (year): |_|_|_| ||_|_|_|

2.3 Have you ever had treatment with blood derivatives/component (e.g. red blood cell concentrate or suspension, platelets, plasma, cryoprecipitate, albumin, coagulation factors, immunoglobulins) ? |_| (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)
If yes, when it was the last one (year): |_|_|_| ||_|_|_|

2.4 Have you ever had dialysis treatment? |_| (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)
If yes, when it was the last one (year): |_|_|_| ||_|_|_|

2.5 Have you ever had endoscopic procedures? (e.g. colonoscopy, oesophagus-gastro-duodenoscopy, bronchoscopy, arthroscopy, etc.)? |_| (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)
If yes, when it was the last one (year): |_|_|_| ||_|_|_|

2.6 Have you ever had intramuscular or intravenous administration of any substance with non-sterile syringes/devices? |_| (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)
If yes, when it was the last one (year): |_|_|_| ||_|_|_|

2.7 Have you ever had acupuncture with non-disposable devices? |_| (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer) If yes, when it was the last one (year): |_|_|_| ||_|_|_|

2.8 Have you ever had tattoos or piercing? |__| (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)
If yes, when you donated blood last time (year): |__| |__| |__| |__|

2.9 Are you blood donor? |__| (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)
If yes, when you donated blood last time (year): |__| |__| |__| |__|

2.10 Have you ever had dental treatment, intervention or dental surgery? |__| (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer) If yes, when it was the last one (year): |__| |__| |__| |__|

2.11 Have you ever been vaccinated against Hepatitis B? |__| (0=No, 1=Yes, 9=Unknown/Refuse to answer)

2.12 Have you ever been vaccinated against Human Papilloma Virus?

2.12.1 If yes, when did you get the vaccine?

year |__| |__| |__| |__|

age |__| |__|

Only for women

2.13 Have you ever been pregnant? (Please consider pregnancies that lasted at least 5 months) |__| (0=No, 1=Yes, 9=Refuse to answer)

If yes:

2.13.1 How many babies have you had? (Please consider babies born alive or dead after 5 months pregnancy) |__| |__|

Would you like to comment or add more details?.....

Part 3: Family medical history [N.B. data can be abstracted from the medical records]

3.1 Please list the number of brothers, sisters, sons and daughters that you have (exclude step-brothers and step-sisters):

Brothers |__| Sisters |__| Sons |__| Daughters |__|

3.2 Did any of your close relatives (those listed above plus your parents), living in the same household, ever suffer from Hepatitis B, C, D? |__| (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

3.3 Did any of your close relatives (those listed above plus your parents) ever suffer from cancer? |__| (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer).

If yes:

Relative (code 1-6) 1=Father / 2=Mother 3=Brother / 4=Sister 5=Son / 6=Daughter	Age at diagnosis	Cancer site (text)	Cancer site (ICD-0-3 code) [To the interviewer - ICD-0-3 code is added during data extraction]
__	__ __		C __ __ __
__	__ __		C __ __ __
__	__ __		C __ __ __

Would you like to comment or add more details?.....

Part 4: Occupational history [N.B. data can be abstracted from the medical records]

Please list below any occupations or jobs you have held for at least 10 years. If you had more than one occupation for 10 years or more, then start with the first job you had after you left school.

OCCUPATION NUMBER |__|

4.1 From: year | | | | to year | | | | and/or
From: age | | | to age | | |

4.2 Occupation / Job title:

.....

4.3 Main activity of the company [if self-employed, state so]:

.....

4.4 Your main type of activity at this job:

.....

4.5 Were you exposed to any biological hazards (human tissue, organs, blood, biological fluids, etc)?
|__| (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=Don't know)

If yes:

4.5.1 Have you received specific OHS training? |__|
(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=refuse to answer/Don't know)

4.5.2 Do you wear personal protective equipment? |__|
(0=No; 1=Yes; 9= refuse to answer/Don't know)

4.5.3 Did you experience any injurie with biological contamination risk (prick, cut, etc.)? |__|
(0=No; 1=Yes; 9= refuse to answer/Don't know)

[To the interviewer: Repeat above questions for as many occupations as necessary]

Would you like to comment or add more details?.....

**THE INTERVIEW IS FINISHED.
THANK YOU FOR YOUR COLLABORATION!**

SELF-REPORTED HEALTH STATUS

Which statement would best describe your health status?

- I generally feel absolutely healthy.
- I only experience minor health issues from time to time.
- I have major and/or chronic health issues.
- I am constantly sick.

Which statement would best describe your understanding of health, health practices, and health issues?

- I am fully aware of my health issues and also have a solid understanding of other health matters.
- I am fully aware of my health issues, their causes, and how I should take care of myself.
- I understand I have some health issues, but I don't know exactly why and what to do about it.
- My doctor tells me that I have severe health issues, but I do not really understand what it means and what I should do with this.

Things that happen in my life most often depend on (Please mark your answer on the scale which applies to you).

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Circumstances, situations, and other people									My own decisions, efforts, and behavior

To what extent do you feel responsible for your health? (Please mark your answer on the scale which applies to you).

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
To very little extent									To a great extent

Do you have a group of close friends you feel you belong to?

0=No; 1=Yes

If yes, how often do you meet your close friends?

(0=Never; 1=Less than once a month; 2=Once a month; 3=Few times per month; 4=Few times per week; 5=Everyday/Daily)

Do you have savings/financial funds that (in case of losing your income) could cover your expenses for at least 3 subsequent months?

0=No 1=Yes 9=prefer not to disclose

Would you like to comment or add more details?.....

DIET

How often do you usually eat the following food items?

(1=never; 2=less than once a month; 3=1-3 times a month; 4=once or twice a week; 5=most days but not every day; 6=every day; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

- Red meat (i.e. beef, veal, pork, lamb, mutton, horse, and goat meat) If red meat consumed:
- Poultry (i.e. chicken and turkey)
- Processed* meat, including hams, salami, sausages, etc.
- Fish

- Fresh fruits (i.e., apples, pears, orange and other citrus fruits, bananas, berries, etc.)
 - Raw vegetables (i.e., green salads, tomatoes, etc., when in season)
 - Cooked green/leafy vegetables (i.e., spinach, artichokes, asparagus, green beans, etc.)
 - Dairy products (i.e., milk, yoghurts, cheese, butter, etc.)
 - Cookies, biscuits, chocolates, cakes and sweets
 - Soft drinks (e.g., cola)
- *Salted, smoked, or processed with any other preservation method.

Would you describe your diet as healthy? 0 = No; 1 = Somewhat; 2 = Yes

Would you like to comment or add more details?.....

TOBACCO USE

Did you smoke cigarettes in the past year?

- No
- Yes
- refuse to answer

If yes:

How many cigarettes per day on average? (ignore vaping, pipe, cigars; include hand rolled)

At what age did you start smoking? (i.e., using cigarettes on most days) |

How many years have you smoked? |

If no:

Have you ever smoked cigarettes on most days for at least one year?

- No
- Yes
- refuse to answer

How many cigarettes did you smoke per day on average? (ignore pipe and cigar smoking; "cigarettes" include hand rolled) |

At what age did you start smoking on most days? |

At what age did you stop smoking? |

Are there any other comments you would like to make with regard to tobacco use?

ALCOHOL USE

Do you drink any alcohol?

- No
- Yes
- refuse to answer

If yes:

How many days per week would you have some alcohol? |
(from 0-7, 0 means none in most weeks)

How much of the following alcoholic beverages do you usually drink per week?

Whiskey/vodka or other strong drinks (40% ethanol)

Quantity/week: | | Unit: glasses bottles

Wine

Quantity/week: |__|__ ||__|__ | Unit: glasses bottles

Beer

|__|__ ||__|__ | bottles/week

[Note to contributing study sites: "glasses", i.e. standard drink volume, and "bottle" volumes to be defined locally]

Are there any other comments you would like to make with regard to alcohol use _____

OTHER SUBSTANCES USE

[Note to the study centre: this is a list of "drugs" recommended for survey purposes by Global Assessment Programme on Drug Abuse (GAP). Drugs are exemplified with street names and/or pharmaceutical names. It is important that all these names are amended to ensure that they are appropriate and understandable in the cultural settings. The list contains "real drugs" but also a fake one (Relevin) to test for honesty of responses. If reported use of the non-existent drug is low, it indicates that subjects do not exaggerate their drug use]

How many times IN YOUR LIFE (if any) have you used any of the following drugs?

Mark one box in each row.

Substances/Drugs	Never	Tried once or twice	Irregular use	Regular use (weekly, monthly, yearly)
(a) Marijuana (grass, pot) or hashish (hash, hash oil)				
(b) Tranquillizers or sedatives (without a doctor/medical worker telling you to do so)				
(c) Amphetamines (uppers, pep pills, bennies, speed)				
(d) Methamphetamine				
(e) Ecstasy				
(f) LSD				
(g) Other hallucinogens (for example "magic mushrooms")				
(h) Relevin				
(i) Cocaine				
(j) Crack				
(k) Heroin (smack, horse)				
(l) Other opiates (without a doctor or medical worker telling you to do so)				
(m) Drugs by injection with a needle (for example, heroin, cocaine, amphetamine)				
(n) Solvents or inhalants (glue, etc.)				

Are there any other comments you would like to make with regard to other substances use?

SEXUAL HABITS

Do you identify as:

Gay

Lesbian

Straight

Bisexual

Other

Have you ever been/are you sexually active with another person?

No

Yes

refuse to answer

If yes:

What is/are the gender(s) of your sex partner(s)? M; F; other;

How many sexual partners have you had in the last year? |

Do you and your partner(s) use STI prevention tools (male/female condoms, other tools)?

No

Yes

refuse to answer

Have you been tested for HIV within the last year?

No

Yes

refuse to answer

If yes: the results of the test were:

positive |

negative |

unknown/refuse to answer |

Have you been tested for sexual transmitted infections within the last year?

No

Yes

refuse to answer

If yes: the results of the test were:

positive |

negative |

unknown/refuse to answer |

Have you ever been tested for Hepatitis? |

No

Yes

refuse to answer

If yes:

When was the test | / | | / | | | (DD/MM/YYYY)

The results of the test were:

positive

negative

unknown/refuse to answer

What type of test it was?

for hepatitis B

for hepatitis C

I do not remember/ I do not know

Where did you get tested:

GP physician

Occupational health physician

Blood donation

- other please specify
 Did you pay for the test?
 yes
 No
 do not remember/refuse to answer

Are there any other comments you would like to make?.....

OTHER ASPECTS

Have you ever living in any type of enclosure setting, deprived of liberty (i.e. war/labor camps, social, mental care facilities etc)?

- No
 Yes
 refuse to answer
 If yes, when it was (year): ||||
 For how long you have been in the enclosure setting?

Have you ever been in prison?

- No
 Yes
 refuse to answer
 If yes, when it was (year): ||||
 For how long you have been in prison?

Is religious/spiritual practice important to you?

- Never
 Yes, still
 Yes, only in the past
 Unknown/refuse to answer
 If yes (current and past)
 How often is/was it?
| | Number of times per week
| | How long is/was it? (min each time)
 At what level do you usually practice?
 Individual
 Family
 Social network
 Organized events

Are there any other comments you would like to make? _____

OPINION ON HCV TESTING AND CANCER PREVENTION AT WORKPLACE

Before entering this study was you aware of the risk factors for liver cancer?

- No
 Yes
 refuse to answer

Before entering this study was you aware of the risks of HCV infection? |

- No
 Yes
 refuse to answer

If yes, from where did you get the information:
 GP physician

- Occupational health physician
- Other physician
- Colleagues/ friends
- Social media
- Mass media (TV, Radio, papers)
- other

Are you positive about carrying out the HCV testing in the workplace?

- No
- Yes
- Unknown/refuse to answer

Do you think this will make it easier to implement for you?

- No
- Yes
- Unknown/refuse to answer

Do you think you were given adequate information before taking the screening test?

- No
- Yes
- Unknown/refuse to answer

If you test positive for HCV, would you be inclined to undergo antiviral therapy?

- No
- Yes
- Unknown/refuse to answer

Are there any other comments you would like to make? _____

Note to the study centre:

The next part of the questionnaire needs to be pre-labelled with the participant code;
The next part of the questionnaire needs to be mailed at the following address

Department of Business and Management
Att. Anna Schneider-Kamp & Tija Rageliene
Campusvej 55 / 5230 Odense M / Denmark

ID number – The same as for the self-admin questionnaire

Note to the participant:

Consider the big circle below as a representation of your general health. Examine the list provided and indicate the importance you attribute to each item for your health within the big circle. Use circles of varying sizes to signify their importance. Label each circle with the corresponding number from the list. For example, if a participant considers their age highly relevant to their health, their job role somewhat relevant, and their neighbours nearly irrelevant, that participant might draw something like this:

Example list and drawing.

1. My age
2. My job role
3. My neighbors

Now, please proceed as follows: First, examine the list numbered 1 to 12 below. Then, draw the circles to illustrate the importance of each item to your health. Finally, label each circle with the corresponding number from the list.

How important are each of these for your health?

1. Relationships with my family members
2. Relationships with my friends
3. Diseases in my family's history
4. Communication with health care specialists (for ex. GP, nurses, doctors, etc.)
5. Foreign languages I can understand.
6. Availability of information about health and diseases
7. Government attention/support to the health care system
8. My income
9. High quality food (for ex. organic, ecological)
10. Availability of new digital technologies OR technologies that I use (PC, web, smartwatch, mobile...).
11. My education
12. How well I can handle stress.

My Health

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COLLABORATION!

16.4 Annex 4 Protocol to assess worker's self-perceived health capital

University of Southern Denmark / Department of Business and Social Science

Projective Technique to Assess Worker's Self-Perceived Health Capital

CPW WP5 Research Protocol

Projective techniques are an approach to gaining insights into people's understandings and imageries in contexts where the response to a direct questionnaire may be complex to obtain or where socially acceptable, but not necessarily truthful responses might be expected. There is a wide range of projective techniques with a common origin in clinical psychiatry that have been adapted and are currently being used in social sciences. Projective techniques are employed in varying degrees in consumer, education and health research since they allow participants to express those thoughts and feelings that can be difficult to access by direct questioning. This is achieved by presenting participants with ambiguous verbal or visual stimulus materials. Importantly, projective techniques can also be fun and therefore engaging for participants to perform (Belk, Ger & Askegaard 1997; Catterall & Ibbotson, 2000; Gambaro, 2018; Wiehagen et al., 2007).

Therefore, projective techniques might be a suitable methodology to be employed for research on health-related topics in different cultural settings, particularly in those settings where qualitative data collection might prove difficult because of the language barrier. *The aim of using the expression as projective circle technique is to explore workers' perceptions of the social, cultural, economic resources, and personal antecedents constituting their health capital* (Schneider-Kamp, 2021; Schneider-Kamp et al. 2021; Schneider-Kamp and Askegaard, 2022; Schneider-Kamp et al. 2023). See figure 1 for an illustration of the patient-centric parts of the health capital model.

Fig. 1. The health capital model underlying the proposed projective circle technique.

Procedure: After filling the baseline questionnaire, participants will be asked to perform a projective technique task. Using the proposed projective circle technique, the participants will be asked to think about different health-related aspects that serve as proxies for the resources that comprise health capital. The participants are tasked to draw these aspects as the smaller circles inside the bigger circle which represents their overall health. The collected data will be sent by post to SDU researchers, where it will be coded in terms of the relative size of different circles drawn by the participants. This means that each circle size is coded by comparing it with other circle sizes inside the big circle which represents the overall health of a participant. The sizes are coded into up to 5 categories: *very large*, *large*, *medium*, *small*, and *very small*. Then this data will be analyzed together with the data collected through the baseline questionnaire.

Tools: Paper and pencil

Method: self-administered

Participants: N=300

Duration: 5-10 min

Instructions to the participant (worded as clearly and simple as possible):

“Consider the big circle below as a representation of your general health. Examine the list provided and indicate the importance you attribute to each item for your health within the big circle. Use circles of varying sizes to signify their importance. Label each circle with the corresponding number from the list. For example, if a participant considers their age highly relevant to their health, their job role somewhat relevant, and their neighbors nearly irrelevant, that participant might draw something like this:

Example list and drawing.

1. My age
2. My job role
3. My neighbors

Now, please proceed as follows: First, examine the list numbered 1 to 12 below. Then, draw the circles to illustrate the importance of each item to your health. Finally, label each circle with the corresponding number from the list.

How important are each of these for your health?

1. Relationships with my friends
2. Relationships with my family members
3. Diseases in my family's history
4. Communication with health care specialists (for ex. GP, nurses, doctors, etc.)
5. Government attention/support to the health care system
6. Availability of information about health and diseases
7. My educational background
8. Foreign languages I can understand.
9. Access to digital technologies (e.g., smartphone, computer fitness tracker)
10. Money for buying medicine and paying for health services
11. Money for purchasing healthy high-quality foods (e.g., organic, ecological)
12. How well I can handle stress.

Example of the task performed.

References

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16.5 Annex 5 Subject log-sheet

SUBJECT LOG-SHEET

Subject ID |__| |__| / |__| |__| |__| |__| / |__| |__| |__| |__| / |__|

Country ID_

centre acronym_

WP number

current number of the index subject_

family member of the index subject__

Example:

RO_COL HOSP_WP3_0001 = index subject from Colentina Hospital, Romania, recruited for HCV

RO_COL HOSP_WP3_0001_01 = family member of the RO_COL HOSP_WP3_0001, recruited for HCV

Subject status: |__|

0=non-eligible

1=index participant (worker)

2=participant (family member)

3=refusal (refuse questionnaire, blood testing and follow-up)

Baseline Questionnaire |__|

(0=no/missing; 1=Yes; 2=pending; 9= refuse to answer the questionnaire)

Follow-up Questionnaire |__|

(0=no/missing; 1=Yes; 2=pending; 9= refuse to answer the questionnaire)

Materials collected for EIAs |__|

(0=no/missing; 1=Yes; 2=pending; 9= refuse biological sampling)

If yes:**Whole blood**

Number of samples |__|

Collection date |__| |__| DD |__| |__| MM |__| |__| YY

Date sent to laboratory |__| |__| DD |__| |__| MM |__| |__| YY

Processed blood

Number of plasma tubes |__|

Number of serum tubes |__|

Collection date |__| |__| DD |__| |__| MM |__| |__| YY

Date sent to laboratory |__| |__| DD |__| |__| MM |__| |__| YY

Results of EIAs test

Note for study centre – please insert results according to the producer specification. For ex:

|__| Positive

|__| Negative

|__| Other

Date of test results |__| |__| DD |__| |__| MM |__| |__| YY

Date of test results communicated to the subject |__| |__| DD |__| |__| MM |__| |__| YY

Results of RDTs test (according to the producer specification)

Note for study centre – please insert results according to the producer specification. For ex:

|__| Positive

|__| Negative

|__| Other

Date of test results |__| |__| DD |__| |__| MM |__| |__| YY

Date of test results communicated to the subject |__| |__| DD |__| |__| MM |__| |__| YY

How was the positive subject linked with the pathway for precise diagnosis and cure?

|__| via GP/family doctor

|__| via gastroenterologist/infectious disease doctor/other specialists

|__| directly, within the project implementation centre

|__| other, please describe

16.6 Annex 6 Clinical diagnosis and treatment data

CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT DATA

Note: the study centre team will seek to extract data from medical charts, GP/gastroenterologist/infectious disease reports, whichever is available according to the local procedure/protocol

Subject ID |__| |__| / |__| |__| |__| |__| / |__| |__| |__| |__| / |__|

Country ID_

centre acronym_

WP number

current number of the index subject_

family member of the index subject__

Example:

RO_COL HOSP_WP3_0001 = index subject from Colentina Hospital, Romania, recruited for HCV

RO_COL HOSP_WP3_0001_01 = family member of the RO_COL HOSP_WP3_0001, recruited for HCV

Hospital/health care setting name:

Local medical record number:

Treating physician and contact details:

.....

GP and contact details:

.....

DIAGNOSIS INFORMATION [Note to the study centre: information marked with * are optional]

HCV viraemic infection |__|

(0=not detected; 1=detected; 9=unknown/pending)

How was the HCV viral load detected:

Laboratory based HCV-RNA quantitative test |__|

Test result (according to producer specifications)

Reference date when appropriate (DD/MM/YYYY): |__| |__| / |__| |__| / |__| |__| |__| |__|

Laboratory based HCV-RNA qualitative test |__|

Test result (according to producer specifications)

Reference date when appropriate (DD/MM/YYYY): |__| |__| / |__| |__| / |__| |__| |__| |__|

Laboratory based HCV core antigen |__|

Test result (according to producer specifications)

Reference date when appropriate (DD/MM/YYYY): |__| |__| / |__| |__| / |__| |__| |__| |__|

Other (please specify) |__|

Test result (according to producer specifications)

Reference date when appropriate (DD/MM/YYYY): |__| |__| / |__| |__| / |__| |__| |__| |__|

*Detected genotype (if available)

*Assessment of co-infection with HIV, HBC, other hepatitis viruses (if available)

HIV-1/2 antigen-antibody immunoassay

Test result (according to producer specifications)

Reference date when appropriate (DD/MM/YYYY): |__| |__| / |__| |__| / |__| |__| |__| |__|

Hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg)

Test result (according to producer specifications)

Reference date when appropriate (DD/MM/YYYY): |_|_|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|_|_|_|_|

Hepatitis B core antibody (anti-HBc)

Test result (according to producer specifications)

Reference date when appropriate (DD/MM/YYYY): |_|_|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|_|_|_|_|

Hepatitis B surface antibody (anti-HBs)

Test result (according to producer specifications)

Reference date when appropriate (DD/MM/YYYY): |_|_|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|_|_|_|_|

***Elastography (i.e., FibroScan test) assessment of liver fibrosis**

F0 = normal

F1-3 = fibrosis (mild/moderate/severe)

F4 = cirrhosis

Clinical diagnosis (ICD 10, version 2019)

|_|_|_|_|_|_|_|_|_|

B16 Acute hepatitis B

B16.0 Acute hepatitis B with delta-agent (coinfection) with hepatic coma

B16.1 Acute hepatitis B with delta-agent (coinfection) without hepatic coma

B16.2 Acute hepatitis B without delta-agent with hepatic coma

B16.9 Acute hepatitis B without delta-agent and without hepatic coma

Acute hepatitis B (viral) NOS

B17 Other acute viral hepatitis

B17.0 Acute delta-(super)infection in chronic hepatitis B

B17.1 Acute hepatitis C

B17.2 Acute hepatitis E

B17.8 Other specified acute viral hepatitis; Hepatitis non-A non-B (acute)(viral) NEC

B17.9 Acute viral hepatitis, unspecified; Acute hepatitis NOS; Acute infectious hepatitis NOS

B18 Chronic viral hepatitis

The following fifth-character subdivisions are for use with categories B18.0-B18.1 and provided for optional use in a supplementary character position.

0 immune-tolerant phase

9 other and unspecified phases

B18.0 Chronic viral hepatitis B with delta-agent

B18.1 Chronic viral hepatitis B without delta-agent; Hepatitis B (viral) NOS

B18.2 Chronic viral hepatitis C

B18.8 Other chronic viral hepatitis

B18.9 Chronic viral hepatitis, unspecified

B19 Unspecified viral hepatitis

B19.0 Unspecified viral hepatitis with hepatic coma

B19.9 Unspecified viral hepatitis without hepatic coma; Viral hepatitis NOS

K73 Chronic hepatitis, not elsewhere classified

K74 Fibrosis and cirrhosis of liver
 C22 Malignant neoplasm of liver and intrahepatic bile ducts
 Z20.5 Contact with and exposure to viral hepatitis
 Z22.8 Carrier of other infectious diseases
 Z22.9 Carrier of infectious disease, unspecified

TREATMENT INFORMATION

Direct Antiviral Agents (DAA) |__|

0=not recommended; 1=recommended; 9=unknown

If recommended:

Date of starting treatment (DD/MM/YYYY): |__||__||/|__||__||/|__||__||__||__||

Date of ending treatment (DD/MM/YYYY): |__||__||/|__||__||/|__||__||__||__||

Cost covered by:

- Health insurance system
- Project team
- Employer
- Other (please specify)

Interferon |__|

0=not recommended; 1=recommended; 9=unknown

If recommended:

Date of starting treatment (DD/MM/YYYY): |__||__||/|__||__||/|__||__||__||__||

Date of ending treatment (DD/MM/YYYY): |__||__||/|__||__||/|__||__||__||__||

Cost covered by:

- Health insurance system
- Project team
- Employer
- Other (please specify)

Ribavirin |__|

0=not recommended; 1=recommended; 9=unknown

If recommended:

Date of starting treatment (DD/MM/YYYY): |__||__||/|__||__||/|__||__||__||__||

Date of ending treatment (DD/MM/YYYY): |__||__||/|__||__||/|__||__||__||__||

Cost covered by:

- Health insurance system
- Project team
- Employer
- Other (please specify)

Others

Please specify.....

Date of starting treatment (DD/MM/YYYY): |__||__||/|__||__||/|__||__||__||__||

Date of ending treatment (DD/MM/YYYY): |__||__||/|__||__||/|__||__||__||__||

Cost covered by:

- Health insurance system
- Project team
- Employer
- Other (please specify)

POST TREATMENT EVALUATION [Note to the study centre: information marked with * are optional]

Treatment efficacy (test of cure): Sustained Virologic Response (SVR)

HCV viral load testing at:

12 weeks (12 weeks after completion of therapy)

Results (according to producer specifications) i.e.

Not detectable

Detectable, not quantifiable

Detectable, quantifiable

*24 weeks (24 weeks after completion of therapy)

Results (according to producer specifications) i.e.

Not detectable

Detectable, not quantifiable

Detectable, quantifiable

*48 weeks (48 weeks after completion of therapy)

Results (according to producer specifications) i.e.

Not detectable

Detectable, not quantifiable

Detectable, quantifiable

16.7 Annex 7 Follow up questionnaire

FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONNAIRE

Subject ID |__| |__| / |__| |__| |__| |__| / |__| |__| |__| |__| / |__|

Country ID_

centre acronym_

WP number

current number of the index subject_

family member of the index subject_

Example:

RO_COL HOSP_WP3_0001 = index subject from Colentina Hospital, Romania, recruited for HCV

RO_COL HOSP_WP3_0001_01 = family member of the RO_COL HOSP_WP3_0001, recruited for HCV

Date of follow up interview: |__| |__| / |__| |__| / |__| |__| |__| |__| (DD/MM/YYYY)

Contacted via |__| 1=direct interview; 2=telephone; 3=(e)mail; 4=other

Subject status: |__|

1=participant (worker) positive at the HCV screening test

2=participant (family member) positive at the HCV screening test

3=refusal

If "3" please explain reason of refusal.....

1. Have you follow the medical recommendation to perform precise diagnosis for HCV infection confirmation in a medical unit/hospital/laboratory? |__| 0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer

If no, please explain the reason:

|__| the health care setting recommended was far from my residence

|__| the health care services recommended where too expensive for me

|__| I do not have medical insurance coverage

|__| I postponed the investigations due to personal problems

|__| other

2. Have you follow the medical recommendation to perform precise diagnosis for associated liver disease in a medical unit/hospital/laboratory? |__| 0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer

If no, please explain the reason:

- |__| the health care setting recommended was far from my residence
- |__| the health care services recommended where too expensive for me
- |__| I do not have medical insurance coverage
- |__| I postponed the investigations due to personal problems
- |__| other

3. Have you follow the medical recommendation to initiate the treatment for the HCV infection in a medical unit/hospital? |__| 0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer

If no, please explain the reason:

- |__| the health care setting recommended was far from my residence
- |__| the treatment recommended was too expensive for me
- |__| I do not have medical insurance coverage
- |__| I postponed the treatment due to personal problems
- |__| other

4. Have you finalized the treatment for the HCV infection? |__| 0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer

If no, please explain the reason:

- |__| I didn't tolerate the treatment
- |__| the treatment recommended was too expensive for me
- |__| I do not have medical insurance coverage
- |__| I interrupted the treatment due to personal problems
- |__| other

5. Have you attended the post-treatment evaluation visit recommended by your treating physician? |__| 0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer

If no, please explain the reason:

- |__| the health care setting recommended was far from my residence
- |__| the health care services recommended where too expensive for me
- |__| I do not have medical insurance coverage
- |__| I postponed the investigations due to personal problems
- |__| other

6. In the future, if your treating physician recommend you to attend monitoring visit, would you accept it? |__| 0=no; 1=yes; 9=refuse to answer

If no, please explain the reason:

- |__| the health care setting recommended was far from my residence
- |__| the health care services recommended where too expensive for me
- |__| I do not have medical insurance coverage
- |__| I consider myself cured
- |__| other

16.8 Annex 8 Questionnaire for occupational health providers - baseline

Measure: Occupational Healthcare Providers

In the CPW project, new screening practices are implemented in occupational health settings. These are not obligatory by law or regulations, but they could have benefit for individual and population health. This questionnaire aims to document problems and chances for a successful implementation from the perspective of occupational physicians and nurses involved in the delivery of the intervention. Please respond to as many questions as possible. If you truly feel you are not able to answer a question, you may select “Do not know.”

The following questions are about you, your current employment, or your role in the CPW project. Please answer as many questions as possible.

A. Characteristics of participants	
Current Date	__ . __ . 20__
Country	<input type="checkbox"/> Italy <input type="checkbox"/> Spain <input type="checkbox"/> Romania <input type="checkbox"/> Slovakia
Health Institute Company	
CPW – Screening Program (Multiple answers possible)	<input type="checkbox"/> Helicobacteria Pylori <input type="checkbox"/> Hepatitis C <input type="checkbox"/> Human Papilloma Virus
Age	<input type="checkbox"/> below 30 years <input type="checkbox"/> 30 – 39 years <input type="checkbox"/> 40 – 59 years <input type="checkbox"/> 60 years or older
Sex	<input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Non-Binary <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Prefer not to say
Profession	<input type="checkbox"/> Physician <input type="checkbox"/> Nurse <input type="checkbox"/> Residents Physician <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
Years in practice	<input type="checkbox"/> below 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – 19 years <input type="checkbox"/> 20 years or longer
Years in current occupational health team	<input type="checkbox"/> below 1 year <input type="checkbox"/> 1 – 4 years <input type="checkbox"/> 5 years or longer

The following questions are related to the screening program that has been implemented at your health institute. Please answer as many questions as possible.

B. About the new screening procedures in CPW						
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
The proposed new screening procedures come from a reliable source.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
There are many advantages of the new screening procedures with regard to health improvements.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The research evidence for the new screening procedures is sufficiently strong.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I see potential harms of the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The provision of the new screening procedures is sufficiently flexible in practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The provision of the new screening procedures is complex in practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

The following questions are related to the organisational context at your health institute. Please answer as many questions as possible.

C. About the Organisational Context						
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
I have sufficient time in my daily practice to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
My place to work is ready for implementing the new screening procedures (e.g., sufficient facilities for testing).	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Information on the new screening procedures for workers is well-organized.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The head of the occupational healthcare team supports the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The employer(s) support the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Follow-up after screening of workers (if required) is well-organized.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The new screening procedures have sufficient priority in my place to work.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
In previous years, my place to work has generally implemented new procedures fast.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Local opinion leaders support the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The organization provides additional support for implementation of the new screening procedures (e.g. resident physicians).	<input type="checkbox"/>					

The following questions are related to your professional role at your health institute. Please answer as many questions as possible.

D. About my role						
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
My professional attitudes match with the basic principles of the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
From the beginning of the project, I feel involved in the implementation of the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I feel sufficiently competent to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I can exclude individual workers from the new screening procedures for medical reasons.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I perceive resistance from the workers against the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Colleagues in my team convinced me to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I am able to change my operational procedures in daily work to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I feel overstrained with the changes in relation to the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The new screening procedures change my area of work/tasks substantially.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Please complete the following questions if residents' physicians (in training for occupational medicine) are included in the CPW project. Please answer as many questions as possible.

E. About resident physicians						
<i>The involvement of resident physicians ...</i>	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
... increases the capacity to delivery of new occupational health services, such as the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... requires additional coordination and supervision of activities	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... stimulates critical reflection in our team on the new screening practices	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... supports the conduct of scientific research of the new screening practices	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... is essential for a successful implementation of the new screening practices	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... helps to spread the new screening practices among occupational healthcare providers in my country	<input type="checkbox"/>					

**This completes the questionnaire.
Thank you.**

16.9 Annex 9 Questionnaire for occupational health providers – follow-up

Measure: Occupational Healthcare Providers

In the CPW project, new screening practices are implemented in occupational health settings. These are not obligatory by law or regulations, but they could have benefit for individual and population health. This questionnaire aims to document problems and chances for a successful implementation from the perspective of occupational physicians and nurses involved in the delivery of the intervention. Please respond to as many questions as possible. If you truly feel you are not able to answer a question, you may select “Do not know.”

The following questions are about you, your current employment, or your role in the CPW project. Please answer as many questions as possible.

F. Characteristics of participants	
Current Date	__ . __ . 20__
Country	<input type="checkbox"/> Italy <input type="checkbox"/> Spain <input type="checkbox"/> Romania <input type="checkbox"/> Slovakia
Health Institute Company	
CPW – Screening Program (Multiple answers possible)	<input type="checkbox"/> Helicobacter Pylori <input type="checkbox"/> Hepatitis C <input type="checkbox"/> Human Papilloma Virus
Age	<input type="checkbox"/> below 30 years <input type="checkbox"/> 30 – 39 years <input type="checkbox"/> 40 – 59 years <input type="checkbox"/> 60 years or older
Sex	<input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Non-Binary <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Prefer not to say
Profession	<input type="checkbox"/> Physician <input type="checkbox"/> Nurse <input type="checkbox"/> Residents Physician <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
Years in practice	<input type="checkbox"/> below 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – 19 years <input type="checkbox"/> 20 years or longer
Years in current occupational health team	<input type="checkbox"/> below 1 year <input type="checkbox"/> 1 – 4 years <input type="checkbox"/> 5 years or longer

The following questions are related to the screening program that has been implemented at your health institute. Please answer as many questions as possible.

G. About the new screening procedures in CPW						
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
The proposed new screening procedures come from a reliable source.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
There are many advantages of the new screening procedures with regard to health improvements.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The research evidence for the new screening procedures is sufficiently strong.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I see potential harms of the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The provision of the new screening procedures is sufficiently flexible in practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The provision of the new screening procedures is complex in practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

The following questions are related to the organisational context at your health institute. Please answer as many questions as possible.

H. About the Organisational Context						
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
I have sufficient time in my daily practice to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
My place to work is ready for implementing the new screening procedures (e.g., sufficient facilities for testing).	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Information on the new screening procedures for workers is well-organized.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The head of the occupational healthcare team supports the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The employer(s) support the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Follow-up after screening of workers (if required) is well-organized.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The new screening procedures have sufficient priority in my place to work.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
In previous years, my place to work has generally implemented new procedures fast.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Local opinion leaders support the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The organization provides additional support for implementation of the new screening procedures (e.g., resident physicians).	<input type="checkbox"/>					

The following questions are related to your professional role at your health institute. Please answer as many questions as possible.

I. About my role						
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
My professional attitudes match with the basic principles of the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
From the beginning of the project, I feel involved in the implementation of the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I feel sufficiently competent to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I can exclude individual workers from the new screening procedures for medical reasons.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I perceive resistance from the workers against the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Colleagues in my team convinced me to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I am able to change my operational procedures in daily work to implement the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I feel overstrained with the changes in relation to the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The new screening procedures change my area of work/tasks substantially.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Please complete the following questions if residents' physicians (in training for occupational medicine) are included in the CPW project. Please answer as many questions as possible.

L. About resident physicians						
<i>The involvement of resident physicians ...</i>	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
... increases the capacity to delivery of new occupational health services, such as the new screening procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... requires additional coordination and supervision of activities	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... stimulates critical reflection in our team on the new screening practices	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... supports the conduct of scientific research of the new screening practices	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... is essential for a successful implementation of the new screening practices	<input type="checkbox"/>					
... helps to spread the new screening practices among occupational healthcare providers in my country	<input type="checkbox"/>					

G. Program Sustainability Assessment Tool

This tool will enable you to assess your program’s current capacity for sustainability across a range of specific organizational and contextual factors. Your responses will identify sustainability strengths and challenges. You can then use results to guide sustainability action planning for your program.

This tool has been designed for use with a wide variety of programs, both large and small, across different settings. Given this flexibility, it is important for you to think through how you are defining your program, organization, and community before starting the assessment.

Below are a few definitions of terms that are frequently used throughout the tool.

- Program refers to the set of formal organized activities that you want to sustain over time. Such activities could occur at the local, state, national, or international level and in a variety of settings.
- Organization encompasses all the parent organizations or agencies in which the program is housed. Depending on your program, the organization may refer to a national, state, or local department, a non-profit organization, a hospital, etc.
- Community refers to the stakeholders who may benefit from or who may guide the program. This could include local residents, organizational leaders, decision-makers, etc. Community does not refer to a specific town or neighbourhood.

In the following questions, you will rate your program across a range of specific factors that affect sustainability. Please respond to as many items as possible. If you truly feel you are not able to answer an item, you may select “NA.”

For each statement, circle the number that best indicates the extent to which your program has or does the following things.

Environmental Support: Having a supportive internal and external climate for your program								
	To little or no extent			To a very great extent				Not able to answer
1. Champions exist who strongly support the program.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
2. The program has strong champions with the ability to garner resources.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
3. The program has leadership support from within the larger organization.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
4. The program has leadership support from outside of the organization.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
5. The program has strong public support.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA

Funding Stability: Establishing a consistent financial base for your program								
	To little or no extent			To a very great extent				Not able to answer
1. The program exists in a supportive state economic climate.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
2. The program implements policies to help ensure sustained funding.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
3. The program is funded through a variety of sources.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
4. The program has a combination of stable and flexible funding.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
5. The program has sustained funding.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA

Partnerships: Cultivating connections between your program and its stakeholders								
	To little or no extent			To a very great extent			Not able to answer	
	1	2	3	4	5	6		7
1. Diverse community organizations are invested in the success of the program.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
2. The program communicates with community leaders.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
3. Community leaders are involved with the program.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
4. Community members are passionately committed to the program.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
5. The community is engaged in the development of program goals.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA

Organizational Capacity: Having the internal support and resources needed to effectively manage your program and its activities								
	To little or no extent			To a very great extent			Not able to answer	
	1	2	3	4	5	6		7
1. The program is well integrated into the operations of the organization.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
2. Organizational systems are in place to support the various program needs.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
3. Leadership effectively articulates the vision of the program to external partners.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
4. Leadership efficiently manages staff and other resources.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
5. The program has adequate staff to complete the program's goals.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA

Program Evaluation: Assessing your program to inform planning and document results								
	To little or no extent			To a very great extent			Not able to answer	
	1	2	3	4	5	6		7
1. The program has the capacity for quality program evaluation.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
2. The program reports short term and intermediate outcomes.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
3. Evaluation results inform program planning and implementation.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
4. Program evaluation results are used to demonstrate successes to funders and other key stakeholders.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
5. The program provides strong evidence to the public that the program works.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA

Program Adaptation: Taking actions that adapt your program to ensure its ongoing effectiveness								
	To little or no extent			To a very great extent				Not able to answer
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
1. The program periodically reviews the evidence base.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
2. The program adapts strategies as needed.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
3. The program adapts to new science.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
4. The program proactively adapts to changes in the environment.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
5. The program makes decisions about which components are ineffective and should not continue.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA

Communications: Strategic communication with stakeholders and the public about your program								
	To little or no extent			To a very great extent				Not able to answer
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
1. The program has communication strategies to secure and maintain public support.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
2. Program staff communicate the need for the program to the public.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
3. The program is marketed in a way that generates interest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
4. The program increases community awareness of the issue.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
5. The program demonstrates its value to the public.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA

Strategic Planning: Using processes that guide your program's direction, goals, and strategies								
	To little or no extent			To a very great extent				Not able to answer
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
1. The program plans for future resource needs.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
2. The program has a long-term financial plan.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
3. The program has a sustainability plan.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
4. The program's goals are understood by all stakeholders.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
5. The program clearly outlines roles and responsibilities for all stakeh.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA

This completes the questionnaire.
Thank you.

17 FIGURES

Figure 1: The testing algorithm for hepatitis C

Figure 2: Overall flowchart of the implementation study

18 TABLES

Table 1: Description of the implementation centres for HCV

Name of the company where the pilot study is implemented (acronym in the project)	NACE code	Total number of employees	Principal investigator (PI) for the HCV intervention	Contact email for the PI

Table 2: Prevention and health promotion initiatives in the implementation centres

Name of the company (acronym in the project)	Testing program for hepatitis (before the current project)	Other preventive program for hepatitis (before the current project)	Prevention program for cancer (past or current)	Health promotion program (past or current)

Table 3: Resources dedicated to the project in the implementation centres

Name of the company (acronym in the project)	Where will be implemented the pilot intervention				Who will implement the pilot intervention (Number)				
	OHS medical office inside the premises	OHS medical office outside the premises	OHS mobile unit	Others	occupational health specialists	other medical doctors	occupational health nurses	laboratory staff	support staff (IT, statisticians, etc.)

Table 4: Laboratory facilities

Name of the company (acronym in the project)	The CPW team has in place/has access to laboratory facilities for			
	collecting blood samples	processing blood samples	storage/shipment of blood samples	testing blood samples for HCV antibodies using immunoassays tests

Table 5: Link with precise diagnosis and cure

Name of the entity (acronym in the project)	In case of positive workers, how will be ensured the link with precise diagnosis and cure? Please describe the pathway and who is involved	In case of workers with confirmed HCV infection, how do you plan to collect information about diagnosis and treatment? Please describe the source of information and who is involved

19 UPDATES FOLLOWING THE 1ST PROJECT TECHNICAL REVIEW

Point 7.1 is updated as following:

The primary goal of the pilot is to investigate the feasibility, performance and cost-effectiveness of prevention interventions targeted toward HCV related liver cancer, within the framework of occupational health surveillance programs.

The outcomes of the pilot study are:

- prevalence and determinants of HCV infection in different occupational groups (health care workers, retail and service workers, finance workers, metal workers)
- behavioural and sociocultural assessment of the barriers and facilitators of the intervention
- acceptability of the intervention by the recipients: participation rate, acceptance rate
- follow up of positives to assess the adherence to diagnosis procedures and treatment, completion of treatment and cure
- acceptability of the intervention by the deliverers (occupational health providers)

Point 7.2 is updated with a new section

Another expected impact to be considered in the development, evaluation of feasibility and implementation of this new health intervention is the assessment of acceptability as a multi-faceted construct that involves both the intervention recipients and the providers.

At baseline we will assess the acceptability of the intervention within the study subjects and in the follow up we will collect information about adherence to diagnosis and treatment, using standardised questionnaires. Apart from assessing acceptability, we will be able to evaluate other aspects such as dropout rates, all-cause discontinuation, reason for discontinuation and withdrawal rates.

Similar, for health care providers (doctors, nurses) we will use pre- and post-intervention harmonized questionnaires to document problems and chances for a successful implementation from their perspective.

Point 7.7 is updated with a new section

HCV testing is based on well-established approaches (screening for the anti-HCV antibody followed by confirmation of active infection by HCV RNA) that accurately detects HCV infection. There is adequate evidence that first time testing in all adults and periodic testing for those at risk for reinfection are beneficial.

There are potential harms described in relation to screening itself: anxiety, fear of been labelled or discriminated. However, the overall harms of a positive test are considered to be lower than the benefits. In our protocol, we considered two key facilitators to minimise the potential harms: raising awareness and education of both deliverers (research staff) and recipients (workers). Enhanced worker education will be ensured by actively disseminating informative materials (flyers, brochures, newsletter) at workplace, meetings of workers with project staff, before and during the intervention. The deliverers (occupational physicians and nurses) will be trained to gain communication skills and to play the role of a healthcare navigator, guiding positive employees inside the local healthcare system. These activities will minimise the harms and increase the potential benefits by timely linking the initial positive test with complete, precise diagnosis of viraemic infection and treatment. The research team will ensure the confidentiality of all information and no test results will be disclosed without the participant permission.

Point 8 has a new section, *Sample Size Justification*, and the section *Timeline* has been updated. Both sections are in accordance with the CPW Grant Agreement.

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